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Research Article

**FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND INVITRO
EVALUATION OF TIZANIDINE ORAL DISINTEGRATING
TABLETS****Syed Areefulla Hussainy*, Lubna Zeenath, Abdul Sayeed and Faizan Sayeed**
MESCO College of Pharmacy, Mustaidpura, Karwan Road, Hyderabad.**Abstract:**

In the present work, chewable release tablets of Tizanidine were prepared by wet granulation method. All the tablets were subjected to weight variation, drug content uniformity, and hardness, and friability, water absorption ratio, wetting time, dissolution, drug excipients interaction and short-term stability FT-IR spectra of the physical mixture revealed that the drug is compatible with the polymers used. The invitro drug release decreased with optimum amount of super disintegrant in the concentration. The formulation TF6 with SSG showed a maximum release of 99.45 % at 18 min. Analysis of drug release mechanism showed that the drug release from the formulations followed the best fit Higuchi's model of drug release diffusion mechanism and follows First order kinetics. Based on the results of evaluation tests formulation coded TF6 was concluded as best formulation.

Keywords: Oro-disintegrating Tablets, Tizanidine, Sublimation Techniques, Direct Compression Techniques.

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INTRODUCTION:**ORALLY DISINTEGRATING TABLETS**

The concept of Fast dissolving Drug Delivery System emerged from the desire to provide patient with more conventional means of taking their medication. It is difficult for many patients to swallow tablets and hard gelatin capsules. Hence, they do not comply with prescription, which results in high incidence of non-compliance and ineffective therapy¹. In some cases, such as motion sickness, sudden episodes of allergic attacks or coughing and unavailability of water, swallowing conventional tablets may be difficult². Particularly the difficulty is experienced by pediatric and geriatric patients. Such problems can be resolved by means of Fast Dissolving Tablet¹. When put on tongue, this tablet disintegrates instantaneously, releasing the drug, which dissolves or disperses in the saliva.

The center for drug Evaluation and Research states an ODT to be: "A solid dosage form containing medicinal substances, which disintegrate rapidly, usually within a matter of seconds, when placed upon the tongue."

These tablets are distinguished from conventional, sublingual tablets, lozenges and buccal tablets which require more than a minute to dissolve in the mouth². In the literature these are also called orally disintegrating, Orodisperse, Mouth dissolving, Quick dissolving, Fast-melt and rapidly disintegrating tablets and freeze-dried wafers.

Mechanism of ODT drugs³:

Generally, ODTs are formulated to disperse rapidly in the mouth, enabling medication to be swallowed without water, thereby increasing convenience and compliance across a broad range of indications and patient types, including the young, elderly, and active patients. Following dispersion, the formulations are swallowed, and the drug is absorbed in the same way as conventional solid-oral dosage forms.

"However, ODTs may also be used to deliver drugs to the oral cavity, for local action or, in some cases, absorption across the oral mucosa, thereby avoiding firstpass hepatic metabolism and potentially increasing the rate and extent of uptake, and reducing undesirable metabolites," The potential for such pregastric absorption rests largely in the physicochemical characteristics of the drug molecule. The intrinsic taste of the drug is also a significant consideration for all ODT formulations.

Disintegration Mechanisms⁴:

Before a tablet dissolves, it has to disintegrate first, unless the tablet is designed for quick surface erosion. The materials used as disintegrants include starches, agar, amylose, cellulose and its derivatives, gum and its derivatives, gelatin, resins, and silicone compounds. A few mechanisms of action of disintegrants have been proposed. The first mechanism is evolution of gas from an effervescent couple, e.g., sodium bicarbonate with citric acid upon absorption of water. The expansion of gas can be enough to cause the tablet to disintegrate. Another mechanism is swelling of disintegrants by absorbing water to break up the tablet structure.

In the tablet disintegration process, several factors may affect the disintegration. They include the rate of water absorption, porosity of the tablet, processing parameters, and effect of active ingredients, surfactants, binders, and lubricants. Fast disintegration always requires fast absorption of water into the center of the tablet. Thus, having open pore structures inside the tablets is very important for making fast dissolving tablets.

Fig. No.1 Mechanism of Fast Disintegrating Tablets

Water Absorption⁵:

Absorption of water into the tablet is important for binding between granules through liquid bridges and for disintegration of the tablet through swelling or dissolution of excipients & through water solid interactions.

The affinity of a substance to water in its vapor state is generally referred to as hygroscopicity.

Aim and Objective Of Work**Aim:**

To formulate and evaluate oral disintegrating tablets Tizanidine using different superdisintegrants, other excipients and selecting best of them.

Objective:

To design the formula for oral disintegrating tablet.

To incorporate selected model drug candidates in the formula and prepare tablets.

To evaluate the formulated tablets.

By physical parameters and

By *in-vitro* dissolution profile of prepared tablets.

METHODOLOGY:**PREFORMULATION STUDIES⁶**

Pre-formulation studies are performed to investigate the physical and chemical properties of a drug substance alone and also when combined with other substances such as excipients. It is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms.

Analytical methods for the estimation of Tizanidine**Preparation of Calibration Curve of Tizanidine in****Table No 1: Formulation of Oro disintegrating Tablets**

Ingredients (mg)	TF1	TF2	TF3	TF4	TF5	TF6	TF7	TF8	TF9
Tizanidine	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
SLS	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
CCS	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-	-
SSG	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-	-
CP	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40	60
Mg. Stearate	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Mannitol	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Pre gelatinized Starch	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Water	Q.S								
LMH	144	124	104	144	124	104	144	124	104
Total	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

0.1N HCl

Procedure: 100 mg of Tizanidine was accurately weighed and dissolved in 20ml of water into a 100ml volumetric flask and finally the volume was adjust to 100ml with water (1000 µg/ml).

The standard solution of Tizanidine was subsequently diluted with 0.1N Hcl to obtain a series of dilutions containing 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50µg/ml. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured on a spectrophotometer at 230nm using 0.1N HCl as the blank.

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT⁷

The fast dissolving tablets containing Tizanidine were prepared with a total tablet weight of 200mg. The aim of the formulation development was to develop a bioequivalent product with respect to reference product with similar physical, chemical characteristics and similar stability profile. The Reference product has Lactose mono hydrate, Cross carmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate, Magnesium stearate. From the basic literature search, excipients compatibility study and patent, underlying following excipients were selected to initiate the development work:

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :-**1. Preformulation Study:****A. Organoleptic Properties (Color, odour, taste and appearance)****Table No.2 Results of identification tests of drug**

S.NO	Parameter	Drug
1	Color	White to off White color
2	Odour	Odorless
3	Taste	Tasteless
4	Appearance	Crystalline powder

B. Melting point determination: Drug: Tizanidine**Table No.3 Results of Melting point determination test of drug**

Drug	Observed Melting Point
Tizanidine	221-224°C

C. Determination of solubility:

Soluble in methanol, water and DMSO, dimethylsulfoxide, and sparingly soluble in ethanol, propylene glycol, and very slightly soluble in hexane.

Table No.4 Bulk density, Tapped density, % Compressibility index, Hausner ratio and Angle of repose. (Precompression studies)

Formulation code	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Hausner ratio	Carr's index (%)	Angle of repose (θ)
TF1	0.542	0.690	1.273	21.44	44 ⁰
TF2	0.488	0.613	1.25	20.39	44 ⁰
TF3	0.712	0.872	1.22	18.34	31 ⁰
TF4	0.714	0.871	1.21	18.025	32 ⁰
TF5	0.716	0.872	1.21	17.889	36 ⁰
TF6	0.412	0.482	1.169	14.522	32 ⁰
TF7	0.421	0.471	1.118	10.615	38 ⁰
TF8	0.542	0.690	1.273	21.44	44 ⁰
TF9	0.454	0.584	1.286	22.26	41 ⁰

Table No.5 Evaluation of Oro disintegrating Tablets of Tizanidine

Formulation code	Weight variation	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)	Content uniformity	Disintegration Time (min)	Palatability
TF1	200	4.3	0.71	2.5	99.27	2	+
TF2	197	4.2	0.67	2.5	97.15	2.3	+
TF3	197	4.7	0.68	2.6	101.2	2.4	+
TF4	201	4.5	0.65	2.76	97.67	2.2	+
TF5	199	4.6	0.67	2.5	99.42	2.3	+
TF6	200	4.8	0.64	2.6	98.18	1.2	+
TF7	198	5.1	2.2	2.5	102.5	1.7	+
TF8	199	4.4	1.7	2.53	99.4	1.5	+
TF9	200	4.9	0.71	2.57	99.5	1.8	+

Table No. 6: Dissolution studies of Oro disintegrating Tablets of Tizinadine

Time in min	TF1	TF2	TF3	TF4	TF5	TF6	TF7	TF8	TF9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3	34.27	41.27	48.15	36.14	42.15	48.26	36.27	42.25	50.17
6	62.19	58.14	75.27	62.21	69.57	74.38	57.52	64.34	69.38
9	76.24	71.26	84.61	74.35	80.38	85.56	71.22	77.34	82.37
12	84.31	84.57	90.26	80.48	86.26	92.61	82.71	89.64	89.26
15	91.04	91.28	92.37	89.27	91.59	99.26	87.38	94.26	92.64
18	95.37	94.41	96.42	94.12	96.25	99.41	94.17	96.74	97.27

Figure 2. Cumulative % drug released for formulations TF1-TF3

Figure 3. Cumulative % drug released for formulations TF4-TF6

Figure 4. Cumulative % drug released for formulations TF7-TF9

Table No.7: Drug Release kinetics profile

RELEASE KINETICS				
	ZERO	HIGUCHI	PEPPAS	FIRST
	1	2	3	4
	Q Vs T	Q Vs \sqrt{T}	Log C Vs Log T	Log % Remain Vs T
Slope	4.981	24.43	1.447	-0.13
Intercept	26.51	5.855	0.452	2.139
R 2	0.796	0.967	0.782	0.945

Stability Studies

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the tablets of formulation TF6 after 3 Months. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown.

Table No.8 : Results of stability studies of optimized formulation TF-6

S.NO	Parameters	Initial	1 month	2 month	3 month	Limits as per specification
1	40°C/75% RH % Release	99.45	98.52	98.79	97.56	Not less than 85 %
2	40°C/75% RH Assay Value	99.45	98.96	97.22	97.00	Not less than 90 % Not more than 110 %

DISCUSSION:

In the present study an attempt has been to formulate and evaluate ODT matrix tablets of Tizanidine by wet granulation (aqueous granulation) technique, employing Lactose monohydrate, were taken along with pharmaceutically acceptable easily available inert excipients and eleven formulations were prepared. The formulation was subjected to both pre and post formulation studies.

The procured drug sample of Tizanidine was tested for its identification by means of organoleptic properties, melting point, UV spectra and FTIR spectrum. The results were found to be within the limits.

Solubility of drug is important factor affecting its release from drug delivery system. Hence solubility analysis of drug sample of Tizanidine was done. The solubility of the Tizanidine was determined and found to be freely soluble in methanol, sparingly soluble in water.

UV Spectroscopic Analytical Method:

Standard curve of Tizanidine in water as shown above. Wavelength of maximum absorption was found to be 230 nm. The Tizanidine obeyed the Lambert-Beer's law in concentration range of 10-50µg/ml at this wavelength. This is well correlated with the reported value (230nm).

Drug Interaction Study:

The granules prepared by wet granulation method were evaluated for various flow properties. The granules of all batches showed good flow properties evident from the results shown in table-16. The angle of repose values were ranged from 31-44. The Carr's index value ranged from 10.61-22.26 and Hausner's ratio value ranged from 1.11-1.28. Hence they have good flow and free flow ability.

Physical characterization of IR Tablets of Tizanidine:

Tablet thickness, hardness, weight variation, friability and drug content of formulated Tablets of batches from TF1 to TF9 are shown in Table No.1.

Uniformity of weight:

All the prepared tablets of Tizanidine were evaluated for weight variation. The weight of all the tablets was found to be uniform with low values of standard deviation and within the prescribed IP limits of $\pm 7.5\%$.

Hardness and friability:

The hardness of the tablet formulations was found to

be in the range of

4.1 to 6.3 kg/cm². The friability values were found to be within the range

Uniformity of drug content:

The low values of standard deviation indicates uniform drug content within the tablets. The percent drug content of all the tablets was found to be in the range of 99.04 to 102.5 percent (which was within the acceptable limits of $\pm 5\%$).

In vitro dissolution study:

In vitro dissolution studies were performed in 0.01N HCl on the above promising formulation, namely, formulation 6. The results are shown in above table. In the dissolution studies, the maximum drug release was found to be with formulation TF6 of maximum drug release (99.41%).

Release kinetics

The release kinetics follow First order and Higuchi is model of kinetics with an R² of 0.945, 0.967 respectively.

Stability Studies:

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the tablets of formulation TF6 after 3 Months, parameters like % drug release and assay values at various conditions (at 40°C/ 75% RH) as per ICH guidelines quantified at various time intervals were shown in above table.

CONCLUSION:

In the present work, Oro disintegrating tablets of Tizanidine were prepared by Direct Compression method. All the tablets were subjected to weight variation, drug content uniformity, and hardness, and friability, water absorption ratio, wetting time, dissolution, drug excipients interaction and short-term stability studies. Formulation TF6 (99.45%) displayed maximum drug release. The optimized formulation follows first order kinetics and Higuchi mechanism of drug release.

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